

Heterogeneous Equilibrium between Solution and Slightly Soluble Compound in Flow Injection Analysis. Equilibrium Constant Determination

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The heterogeneous equilibrium constant between solution and slightly soluble compound under conditions of flow injection analysis is determined in three ways. The constant is not identical to the solubility product. The heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 is defined. It has values over three orders lower than the value of the solubility product. Indication is made that the flow rate exerts an influence on the value of the heterogeneous equilibrium constant

In our previous work¹ we suggested a flow injection method by which the compound to be determined is analysed by the change of the equilibrium between the solution studied and the slightly soluble compound, carried out by passing the solution through a reaction column containing a precipitate. The method is applied for the determination of H_2PtCl_6 , use being made of a column with a slightly soluble salt Tl_2PtCl_6 .

Since the equilibrium process is the basis of this determination, a knowledge of the value of the heterogeneous equilibrium constant is of essential significance for the analysis. The experimental data from the platinum(IV) determination are not in agreement with the data for the solubility product known in the literature. Hence, it may be supposed that the constant of heterogeneous equilibrium between solution and precipitate, under the dynamic conditions of flow analysis, has a value differing from the value of the solubility product.

Flow injection analysis is used as a means for determination of the solubility product², but the constant of heterogeneous equilibrium has not been determined under the above-indicated conditions of flow injection analysis. The purpose of the present work is to develop a method for determining the heterogeneous equilibrium constant. The constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 is defined.

Results and Discussion

The continuous analysis for determination of K , by measuring the solubility of the precipitate, has the advantage that it clearly reflects the time when equilibrium between the solution and precipitate is obtained in the column, and this makes possible a correct determination of the equilibrium concentration of thallium(I). In Fig. 1 is shown the recording of the signals of three standard thallium(I) solutions,

Fig. 1. Analytical readout in determining the heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 from the solubility of the precipitate by use of continuous analysis of thallium(I); flow rate 0.75 ml min^{-1} .

and the signal of the concentration of thallium(I) which is in equilibrium with Tl_2PtCl_6 precipitate. The horizontal part of the curve shows the establishment of a heterogeneous equilibrium. What is characteristic of the determination is that the pulsation in the flow causes oscillations of the signal which are greater for lower flow rates. For higher flow rates the oscillations diminish, but the range of concentrations about which the dependence current—thallium(I) concentration is linear, also decreases. Besides this, curve distortions are obtained immediately before its horizontal part, which causes inaccuracies.

In the determination of K by the solubility of the precipitate with flow injection detection, the problem is to determine correctly the moment when the

dynamic equilibrium in the column has set in, after which a sample of the solution having passed through the column is to be injected. In order to avoid eventual errors from possible incomplete setting in of the equilibrium, it would be necessary to pass the solution through the column more continuously or to apply several injections until the peak heights become constant. An essential advantage of this working scheme (Fig. 2) is that the detection is carried out in a separate flow line under optimal conditions for conducting the analysis. The rate of flow passing through the column does not influence the determination of thallium(I) itself.

Fig. 2. Block-scheme for determining the constant of heterogeneous equilibrium of Tl_2PtCl_6 by use of continuous flow analysis of thallium(I): (1) vessel for water (0.1 M HCl), (2) vessel for standard solutions, (3) three-way valve, (4) peristaltic pump, (5) three-way valve, (6) column with filling of porous glass and Tl_2PtCl_6 , (7) column with porous glass filling, (8) detector and (9) polarograph.

Determination of the heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 by means of flow injection analysis of platinum(IV), is more tedious in comparison with the other two methods since it requires two standard curves for platinum(IV) and thallium(I), respectively. However, the method has an advantage in that the value of K is determined by the experimental data of several standard platinum(IV) solutions, whereas with the other two methods the equilibrium concentration of thallium(I) is obtained by one measurement. Owing to the fact that the platinum(IV) solution is prepared in hydrochloric acid, the determination of K by this method is possible in this medium only.

Thus the different methods of K determination have both their advantages and disadvantages and are mutually complementary. The results for K by the three methods are presented in Table 1. With alteration of the flow from 0.25 to 2.0 $ml\ min^{-1}$ the value of K decreases approximately by one order. The influence of the flow rate may be explained in the following manner: with a lower flow rate a smaller volume of the solution will pass through the column per unit time, the substance dissolved in a smaller volume will have a higher concentration and therefrom the value of the equilibrium constant will be greater. On the contrary, with higher flow rate, the precipitate will be dissolved in a greater volume, the solubility under

TABLE 1—HETEROGENEOUS EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K) DATA

Flow rate $ml\ min^{-1}$	$K \times 10^{-10}$					
	Method 1		Method 2		Method 3	
	in H_2O	in 0.1M HCl	in H_2O	in 0.1M HCl	in 0.1M HCl	
0.25	7.6		9.5			
0.30		7.8		5.2	6.2	
0.50	2.7	4.4	6.0	4.2	4.1	
0.75	2.0	2.5	3.0	2.8	2.6	
1.0	1.3	0.88	2.1	2.0	1.2	
1.5	0.76	0.84	1.1	1.2	0.9	
2.0	0.46	0.72	0.72	0.8	0.78	

the conditions of flow and equilibrium constant will be lower. In both the cases, the dissolving capacity of the precipitate is one and the same and is determined by the solubility product. The solubility product³ of Tl_2PtCl_6 is 4×10^{-12} , while the values of the heterogeneous equilibrium constant determined by us, are more than three orders lower. It becomes clear that the heterogeneous equilibrium constant in flow is not identical to the solubility product. What is significant for carrying out flow injection analysis is not the solubility product but the determined equilibrium constant under the conditions of analysis.

Changing the flow rate is a way for changing the value of heterogeneous equilibrium constant and therefore the condition of performing the precipitation. Thus, flow injection analysis gives possibilities, unrevealed so far, for management of the precipitation reaction.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. The solutions were prepared with distilled water. Deaeration or oxygen elimination from the solutions was not necessary. For carrier solution and as supporting electrolyte, use was made of 0.1 M HCl. A 0.1 M stock solution of thallium(I) was prepared by dissolving of $TlNO_3$ in water. A 0.01 M solution of H_2PtCl_6 was prepared from $(NH_4)_2PtCl_6$ which was previously converted into metal platinum by heating at 230° for several hours, then raising the temperature to 800° and continuing heating at this temperature for 1 h. Platinum (0.195 g) was dissolved at 80–90° in aqua regia (5 ml), then 37% HCl (2 ml) was added and evaporated nearly to dryness and the operation was repeated twice. Then 37% HCl (1 ml) was added and diluted with water to 100 ml. The solutions for analysis were prepared by respective dilution of 0.01 M stock solution of platinum(IV) with 0.1 M HCl.

For the instrumental set-up of the separate schemes for flow and flow injection analysis, use was made of: one or two peristaltic pumps ISMATEC (Switzerland); injection valve TECATOR (Sweden) with an injection loop volume of 200 μl ; the reaction column containing Tl_2PtCl_6 and porous glass, described elsewhere¹; an electrochemical detector cell (cons-

tructed by us) combined with a Radelkis OH-105 polarograph serving at the same time as a potentiostat and as a recorder. The construction of the detector cell and the determination of Tl^I with it has already been described earlier⁴.

Methods :

The constant of heterogeneous equilibrium K of Tl_2PtCl_6 was determined in three ways. In two of these, the constant was calculated from the solubility of the precipitate under the conditions of carrying out flow injection analysis, use being respectively made of continuous flow and flow injection analysis of thallium(I). In the third method, the constant of heterogeneous equilibrium was determined from the experimental data of flow injection analysis of platinum(IV).

Since determinations of platinum(IV) and thallium(I) were carried out in the background of 0.1 M HCl and the platinum(IV) solution itself being in 0.1 M HCl, the equilibrium constant was determined not in water but in 0.1 M HCl.

Method 1. Determination of K from the precipitate solubility by use of continuous flow analysis : Distilled water or 0.1 M HCl was propelled at a constant flow rate through the column (6 ; Fig. 2) containing the slightly soluble compound Tl_2PtCl_6 . The current of thallium(I) concentration in equilibrium with the precipitate was recorded. Then by means of three-way valves (3 and 5) the direction of the flow was changed and standard thallium(I) solutions in water or in 0.1 M HCl were passed to the detector. To ensure the same hydrodynamic conditions, the flow passed through a column (7) packed with porous glass but without Tl_2PtCl_6 sediment. The column with Tl_2PtCl_6 and the solutions were thermostated at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The equilibrium thallium(I) concentration $[Tl^+]$ was determined after the standard curve : current-concentration of thallium(I). Equilibrium constant K was calculated from the equation,

$$K = [PtCl_6^{2-}][Tl^+]^2 = 1/2[Tl^+]^3 \quad (1)$$

In a medium of 0.1 M HCl (for this and other two methods of K determination) K was calculated not from the equilibrium concentrations of platinum(IV) and thallium(I) but from their activities ($a_{PtCl_6^{2-}}$ and a_{Tl^+}),

$$K = a_{PtCl_6^{2-}} \cdot a_{Tl^+}^2 = [PtCl_6^{2-}] [Tl^+]^2 f_{PtCl_6^{2-}} \cdot f_{Tl^+}^2 \quad (2)$$

For ionic strength of 0.1 the activity coefficients $f_{PtCl_6^{2-}}$ and f_{Tl^+} are accepted to be 0.355 and 0.75 respectively⁵.

Method 2. Determination of K from the precipitate solubility by use of flow injection analysis : In this method of K determination (Fig. 3), the flow of water or 0.1 M HCl, passed at a constant rate through the column with Tl_2PtCl_6 , was injected in another flow line with carrier solution of 0.1 M HCl. After turning the valves (3) and (5), standard

Fig. 3. Block-scheme for determining the heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 by flow injection analysis of thallium(I) and platinum(IV) : (1) vessel for water (0.1 M HCl), (2) vessel for standard solutions, (3) three-way valve, (4 4') peristaltic pump, (5) three-way valve, (6) column with porous glass and Tl_2PtCl_6 filling, (7) injection valve, (8) detector and (9) polarograph.

thallium(I) solutions were injected by a by-pass line, without passing of the flow through the column. Response curves of this determination are shown in Fig. 4. The equilibrium concentration of thallium(I) was determined after a standard curve : peak height-thallium(I) concentration. K was calculated by equation (1) or (2).

Fig. 4. Analytical readout in determining the heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 from the solubility of the precipitate by use of flow injection analysis of thallium(I) ; flow rate through the column 2.0 ml min^{-1} , volume of injected sample $200 \mu\text{l}$.

Method 3. Determination of K by flow injection analysis of platinum(IV) : Use was made of the scheme shown in Fig. 2. Standard thallium(I) solutions were injected in the above-described manner. From the linear dependence of the peak height (H) on the

concentration of thallium(I), C_{Tl} was determined from the equation,

$$H = kC_{Tl} \quad (3)$$

where k is the linear regression coefficient. Then standard platinum(IV) solutions were successively passed through column (6) (Fig. 2). When the

equilibrium between the respective platinum(IV) solution and Tl_2PtCl_6 precipitate was established, a sample of the solution passed through the column was injected in the flow line of the carrier 0.1 M HCl solution. The height of the flow injection peak (h) is a linear function of the concentration of platinum(IV) solution¹, $C_{Pt}^{-1/2}$,

$$h = K^{1/2} k C_{Pt}^{-1/2} \quad (4)$$

The linear regression coefficient $s = K^{1/2} k$ was determined from equation (4) (Fig. 5) and using data for k , obtained from equation (3), the heterogeneous equilibrium constant K was calculated.

Fig. 5. Determination of the heterogeneous equilibrium constant of Tl_2PtCl_6 by flow injection analysis of platinum(IV).

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